

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE IDENTITIES OF REPATRIATED MUSLIM MESKHETIANS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

Displacement, the forced change of one's living place, has influenced the cultural and ethnic identity of many peoples' lives. This study examines the life of Muslim Meskhetians, people deported from Georgia to the central Asian republics of the Soviet Union in WWII by Stalin's social policy as "undesirable people".

After 1956 some Muslim Meskhetian families tried to return to their homeland. Formal repatriation of Muslim Meskhetians to Georgia started in 1977. The first wave of repatriated Muslim Meskhetians mostly settled in villages near Samtredia and Ozurgeti. After starting implementation of a new repatriation law in 2012, which was adopted in 2007, repatriated Muslim Meskhetians are living in different districts of Georgia, even in their original homeland in the South-West. Based on theoretical concepts of ethnic identity, place identity, and on the quantitative and qualitative research methods the study analyses of *social identity complexity* (ethnic, civil, and place identity) of Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia.

Keywords: Ethnic identity; Muslim Meskhetians; Civil Identity; Place identity; Ahiska Turks.

Author's Note: *Throughout history, the population I refer to in this study as "Muslim Meskhetians" have been known by many names. Some researchers refer to this population as "Meskhetian Turks," or "Turks from Meskhetia." Oftentimes, they call themselves "Ahiska Turks" (which means Turks from Akhaltsikhe, a central town in Meskheti and part of southwestern region of the Republic of Georgia near the Turkish border). I refer to this population as Muslim Meskhetians, because they are the deported Muslim population from Meskhetia.*

Introduction

Muslim Meskhetians from the South-Western part of Georgia were deported during WWII and scattered around post-soviet republics. Once there, they worked to adapt to each distinct social environment. According to migration researchers, new social environments influence human lifestyle and social identity formation. Integration is the best way for people in a new environment to adapt (Berry, 1997). Several factors can work to support the integration process of displaced persons: their individual skills, their willingness to learn the new language, and their culture (Sam., Berry (2006); Berry (2001); Sammut (2010); Padilla (2004).

The adaptation-integration process in the new environment has an impact on an emigrant's human identity. The formation of identity during the life of an individual is an important process. Identities can shift and transform over time and as contexts change and individuals may consider themselves members of a variety of different social identity groups over the course of a lifetime. (Schwartz, Luyckx, and Vignoles 2013). (Moscovici, 1981).

Many factors dictate an individual's social identity, including social environment, the perception of others, and the roles within primary and secondary social groups. The study of the process of identification takes on special significance when people change their

living environment (Sam & Berry, 2006). Under these circumstances, it is possible to witness how individual ethnic, cultural, and place identities change as a result of migration. Moreover, social identity can be impacted by civic consciousness in the new environment and an emigrant's feelings towards the local society. (Tajfel & Turner, 1979).

This descriptive study presents qualitative and quantitative data on repatriated Muslim Meskhetians inhabiting the Republic of Georgia in order to demonstrate the influence of adaptation and integration on their identities. I seek to contribute to this body of literature by examining of social identity complexity of Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia a detailed analysis of ethnic, civil, and place identity.

About Muslim Meskhetians

The Republic of Georgia was occupied by the Ottoman Empire between 1578 and 1883. Consequently, their religion, way of life, and language changed and they transformed from Georgian-speaking Orthodox Christians to Turkish-speaking Muslims. Despite the fact that Turkish is the primary language of Muslim Meskhetians, both Turkish and Georgian cultural traits are equally identifiable in their cultural identity. (Baramidze, 2011; Janiashvili, 2006)

According to researchers Trier and Khanzhin, Muslim Meskhetians have been known by numerous names over the course of history (2007). Historical records indicate that they were referred to as Georgians [born in Russian-Empire Caucasian Province before 1917 or Socialist Republic of Georgia after the revolution]. Muslim Georgians [a small religious minority in Soviet Georgia where Christianity was predominant], Muslim Meskhetian Turks [dwelling in specific regions throughout Georgia - Meskhetia, and their genealogical links with the Ottomans]. Meskhs [highlighting their geographical district only], Turks [unlike Meskhs highlighting genealogical roots as the key identity marker], Azeri [Soviet administrative classification based on the

religious and linguistic affiliation between Azeri and Turks], Meskhetian Turks [the Stalinist name given to the group later], Ahitska Turks / Akhaltsikhe Turks {the most up to date name the US-based society obtained}.

Dating back to ancient times, Muslim Meskhetians and Orthodox Christian Georgians have shared residence in the Caucasus, including southwest Georgia near the Turkish border. In 1578-1883 AD, this territory was invaded by the Ottoman Empire. As a result of colonization, the inhabitants of Meskheti, Javakheti converted from Orthodox Christianity to Sunni Islam, alongside a shift in language from Georgian to Turkish. After the war between Russia and Turkey (1877-1878), the Ottomans fled from the region and Meskheti later became an integral part of Russia with significant signs of Islamization. Further cataclysmic changes were brought by the Bolshevik Revolution in 1917. For a very limited period, between 1918 and 1921 Georgia was independent. Afterward, the second conflict with Bolshevik Russia brought the loss of independence and Georgia's integration into the USSR. During these politically inconsistent times, the majority of local Muslims allied with the Ottomans and migrated to Turkey (Sumbadze, 2007) (Maglakelidze, 1994; Nozadze 1989). Some Muslim Meskhetians left the borders of the Soviet Union and those who stayed were targeted for Sovietization campaigns.

The Soviet aimed at combining all Muslim-practising nationalities under one unit. All local Turkish-speaking Islamists were referred to as "Azeri" in public documents by the new administration. Muslim Meskhetians, the Khemshis (Muslim Armenians) and Kurds from Georgia were all referred to as "Azeri" in those documents. This way, the Soviets consciously combined Turkish-speaking Georgians with their next-door neighbors, the Azerbaijani. This enabled the Soviets to open Azeri-language schools in Georgia to educate the Muslim youth (Sumbadze, 2007).

During WWII, a wave of mass deportations was initiated by the Soviet Union. The resolution No 6279 issued by the USSR Defense State Committee on July 31st, 1944 and the order N00117 issued by the Ministry of the Internal Affairs on September 20th in the same year were designed to deport 19,818 families from the Georgian SSR, including Turks (14,493 families); Kurds (1,830 families); Azerbaijanians (3,058 families); Yazidis (7 families); Tatars (126 families), and Khemshis/Muslim-Armenians of Laz origin (304 families) (Trier & Khanzhin, 2007). All of the aforementioned Turkish-speaking Muslim groups were forced into cargo-carrying carriages and moved thousands of kilometers away on November 15th, 1944.

Men were mostly mobilized to serve the Red Army of Eastern Front against the Nazis and the women, children and elderly were relocated within Soviet republics of Uzbekistan (roughly 53,163 people), Kyrgyzstan (28,598), and Kazakhstan (10,546) (Bugai, 1994; Sumbadze, 2007). Around 92,307 inhabitants were deported from five administrative districts of Southern Georgia – Samtskhe and Javakheti. Since a great number of people died in the process of their de-

portation, the experience was extremely traumatic. Deported families were not permitted to return to their homes or retrieve their belongings for over four decades. The psychological trauma caused by mass deportation is both deep and pervasive, affecting the social lives of the affected people were shaken again by the new conflict with the local Central Asian population. (Bessel, at all 1987; Ciano 2017)

In 1989, out of 207,500 Muslim Meskhetians who lived in the Soviet Union, over 51.2% were from Uzbekistan (Babak, Vaisman & Wasserman 2004;252). Most Meskhetians moved to Fergana Valley. In June of 1989, a massacre broke out in the Uzbek section of the Ferghana Valley resulting in the death of dozens of Meskhetians (Yunusof 2000;92). The real reason for the massacre is still vague. Following the Soviet Army intervention, the situation was more or less stabilized. However, 17,000 Muslim Meskhetians were instantly evacuated by the Soviet Army troops, causing an outflow of Muslim Meskhetians from Uzbekistan over the next few years. Over 60,000 Meskhetians are estimated to have left after the initial evacuation. Hence, they went through the second inadvertent relocation 45 years after Stalin's deportation. Some Muslim Meskhetians were left homeless (Aydingün, 2002). Others moved to Azerbaijan or Russia, in the Krasnodar region bordering Georgia. A select number of formerly-deported Muslim Meskhetians were able to return to Meskhetia (Ossipov, 2002, Koriouchkina, 2009).

After the Soviet Union dissolution, the Russian Federation ceased issuing Russian-citizenship passports to Muslim Meskhetians, rendering them "illegal" immigrants throughout the territory of Russia. Repatriation to Georgia was not a solution thereupon, neither pragmatically nor legislatively. The U.S.A. offered "refugee" status to all Muslim Meskhetians living in Krasnodar, Russia. Consequently, beginning in 2005, Muslim Meskhetians began relocating into thirty-three of the fifty U.S. states (Koriouchkina & Swerdlow, 2007).

Generally, scholars studying cultural adaptation have come to the following conclusion: the longer a refugee lives away from the homeland the more their cultural values, traditions and lifestyle transform. However, it is worth pointing out that Muslim Meskhetians are often described as unique, having successfully retained many of their cultural attributes despite multiple forced migrations and dislocation experiences (Trier & Khanzhin, 2007).

Today, Muslim Meskhetians live around the world and as part of their integration, they have gained new identities for themselves. For instance, those who live in Azerbaijan identify largely as Turks (Yunusof, 2000), while others, strongly reject any connection with Turkey and highlight their differences, claiming a strict Georgian identification (Sumbadze, 2007). Since their relocation to the United States, they created yet another immigrant ethnic identity, that of the *Akiska Turks*.

In the studies of Avci (2012) and Bal and Arzubiyaga (2013), Muslim Meskhetians are referred to as their ascribed identity *Ahiska Turks*. Preceding these studies, however, non-Georgian scholars used to refer to this population as Meskhetian Turks. As described in

the aforementioned Author's Note, this study of the population in the Republic of Georgia, researchers utilize the term "Muslim Meskhetian" in recognition of the subject population's experience of displacement and current residence.

Theoretical perspectives of social, ethnic, place and civic identities

Membership in various social, ethnic, or cultural groups influences identity. As scholars (Roccas & Brewer 2002) argued "Identity refers to the outcome of two main processes: self-representations and social categorization. The combination of these two processes results in the feeling of differentiation from others, the recognition of one's own difference, the sense of belonging, and consequent mechanisms of inclusion and exclusion, which are in turn created, maintained, and reinforced through public policies and the law".

Identity is an important aspect of personhood and is the product of social, cultural, political, and ethnic constructions. Of note, ethnic identity is determined by many components, and includes the process of searching, acquisition, and strengthening (Umaña-Taylor, 2011; Phinney, 1996). Ethnic identity is tied directly to belonging to specific ethnic groups. The process of recognition involves both being ascribed that ethnic identity by "others" within the ethnic group, as well as "others" outside of the ethnic group. Ethnic identity is considered to be an inborn feature by some, yet others argue that how people ascribe their own identities also influence identity itself. Two approaches are considered the basis for the emergence of ethnic identity. A primordialist (Isajiw, 1993; Smith, 1991) approach claims that ethnic identity is inborn and predefined. Ethnicity is given from birth, assumed to be both solid and permanent. According to a constructive approach, ethnic identity is a choice: what it relies on, what its content is, and the shape it takes is dependent on the free will of an individual. Its basis may be language, religion, culture, race, history, or territory (Simmel, 2011; Barth, 1969). Many psycho-social factors influence the formation of ethnic identity, but perhaps most important is the universal desire of an individual to establish a positive social identity.

Social identity represents an individual's conception of self as defined by social group membership (Turner, Penny, 1986). The specifics of intergroup behavior in the theory of social identity (Tajfel, Turner, 1970) can be explained by the concept of social identity. An individual obtains social identity when the meaning of social group membership is acknowledged and plays an important and positive role in everyday life. Social identity is complex concept; According to scholars (Roccas and Brewer 2002) "the concept of social identity complexity—a new theoretical construct that refers to the nature of the subjective representation of multiple ingroup identities. when individuals may incorporate multiple group memberships in their overall social identity and in their conceptualization of ingroups and outgroups". When person accepted, memberships in multiple ingroups when identity structure is both more inclusive and more complex (Roccas and Brewer 2002).

To describe this type of identity, environmental psychologists use the term "place identity", which is considered part of personal identity and describes people's perception of themselves in relation to specific environmental characteristics (Hernández et al., 2007; Cuba and Hummon 1993a, 1993b).

"Place identity is a complex and dynamic construct, classically defined as an individual's transfer (incorporation) of place into a broader concept of the self; "Memories, concepts, interpretations, ideas, and feelings associated with a particular physical environment (Proshansky, Fabian & Kaminoff, 1983, p. 60).

There are a number of theoretical models related to this construct, and researchers focus on different aspects when defining it, such as a sense of belonging to a place (Dixon et al., 2023), community connection (Sobhaninia et al., 2023; Aton & Lawrence, 2014), interpersonal aspects of identity (Leary & Tangney, 2013), sense of satisfaction with place (Lewicka, 2011) and cognitions formed as a result of psychological connection (Lewicka, 2011). However, each of these models is united by an emphasis on the affective component of place identity - a certain emotional connection of an individual to a place

The existence of diverse definitions of place identity can be considered the main reason why it is difficult to separate it from other central concepts of environmental psychology, such as "place attachment", "sense of place" or "place dependence" (Peng, Strijker, & Wu, 2020). For example, place identity is sometimes considered as one dimension of place attachment (Ujang, N., & Zakariya, 2015). Other authors consider both identity and attachment to be part of a broader construct, sense of place (Jorgensen & Stedman, 2001).

From the perspective of social psychology, place creates the frame of culture and traditions in which identity is constructed, preserved, and transformed (Cuba, Lee, & Hummon, 1993b). Social and environmental psychologists Harold Proshansky, Ebby Fabian, and Robert Kaminoff (Proshansky, Fabian & Kaminoff, 1983) claimed that place identity informs individual social identity, shaped by the experience of daily interaction with physical spaces (Proshansky, 1978).

Places where people live, or lived, acquire different meanings and arouse different feelings and memories. From this point of view, the house is usually one of the most important places, and its change causes changes in the individual's self-identification. When an individual moves from one place to another, their sense of belonging can be threatened (Lewicka, 2011). A person experiences attachment to a place with society, cultural or religious affiliation (Lewicka, 2011).

The move from one geographical location to another can have a positive effect as well as a negative one, especially when this displacement is not voluntary and is related to conditions such as natural disasters, wars, social problems or better educational opportunities (eg, Massey, 2015).

Sometimes it negatively affect a person's psychic condition in the same way the death of a relative, friend, or family member might (Fried, 1963).

Thus, the notion of identity is important in the study of forced migration cases, in particular the case of Muslim Meskhetian after three times of displacement.

The society of Muslim Meskhetians is perhaps of particular uniqueness, in this regard, as their ethnic identity represents the verbalization of a variety of identities: Meskhetian Turks, Turks, Georgians, and Ahiska Turks.

This article studies the Muslim Meskhetians life in the Republic of Georgia. Analysing their identities based on subjective perceptions.

Methodology

This descriptive research study is informed by the general advice of migration scholars who advocate an in-depth examination of the resettlement experience. Firstly, desk research was conducted in order to find out the current features of subject population. After that, the study employed a mixture of both qualitative and quantitative methods. Based on recommendations for selecting the sample size in qualitative research (Creswell, 1998), 60 qualitative in-depth interviews were conducted in sum; 40 out of 60 were carried in participation with Muslim Meskhetians, 10 in-depth interviews were done with experts of this community, and 10 persons who are living in the neighborhood and in local governmental organizations working on the problems of research participants.

According to the information from Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Accommodation and Refugees of Georgia nowadays in Georgia are living approximately 423 Individual Muslim Meskhetians.

Respondents for quantitative research were chosen using the nonprobability sampling methods- available sampling. In areas inhabited by participants, was interviewed everyone who met us at home in order to have access to research participants.

The research study included 250 face-to-face quantitative interviews with Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia and a questionnaire featuring two psychological tests:

(1) Twenty Statements Test (TST; Kuhn and McPartland 1954) – used to measure participants' self-identity, the roles played and the priority of these roles

(2) Bogardus Social Distance Scale (Bogardus 1924) - an instrument used to measure participants' willingness to participate in social contacts of varying degrees of closeness with members of diverse social groups, such as those of other races or ethnicities

Both instruments were adapted by scholars (Sumbadze, Kitiashvili, Pirtskhalava, Maisuradze) in Georgia in 2012.

Participants appeared to be quite comfortable while sharing information about their family structure, relationships, and gender roles. The research group consisted of four Georgian researchers, all of whom were non-Muslim Meskhetians. Notably, the ease of establishing communication with the Muslim Meskhetian community depended on the district and household composition, urban vs. rural village environments, familiarity with the researcher from previous research contact, and language barriers. Because the lead researcher was known to participants from two districts

(she had conducted participant observation in 2004 with Meskhetians in the Nasakirali and Samtredia districts), research conducted with participants from these specific districts was met with greater ease.

Muslim Meskhetians, who returned to Georgia after the adoption of the 2012 Repatriation Law had difficulty communicating in both Georgian and Russian languages, but assistance from an interpreter mitigated language barriers.

Research results

Muslim Meskhetians in Modern Day in Georgia:

Desk Research Results

Muslim Meskhetians, who lived in exile for decades, underwent different repatriation attempts to Georgia over the years. During the first wave of repatriation in the 1970s, they settled in the western part of Georgia, namely in the regions of Samegrelo, Imereti, and Guria. Some repatriates stayed in their homeland and have been living in Samtredia and Ozurgeti villages for more than 40 years. Others live in the capital city of Tbilisi. A small portion returned to the post-soviet Central Asian republic.

In 1999, following a decree from the Council of Europe to return deported people to their homeland, Georgia began working on its repatriation law. On July 11th, 2007, the Parliament of Georgia adopted the law (№ 5261) on the “repatriation of the people exiled from Georgian SSR by former USSR during the ‘40s of XX century.” which was enforced in 2012.

After the adoption of the law, some Muslim Meskhetians did not wait for its enforcement, but entered Georgia and settled in Samtredia and other parts of Akhaltsikhe. Later, after the law's enforcement, Muslim Meskhetians arrived in Georgia by way of repatriation. They obtained Georgian citizenship and some settled in the municipality of Akhaltsikhe and surrounding areas, many of which represent areas from which their ancestors had been deported.

The Muslim Meskhetian community operates as a traditional and closed society, in which individual behavior is determined by historical models that characterize stable social behavior through rules passed from generation to generation. Changes in such a society are slow, as individual behavior is often characterized by a strong adherence to social group norms and influence.

In a Muslim Meskhetian family, traditional male and female roles are defined according to gender. This is due, in part, to the influence of collectivist culture and religion. Muslim Meskhetian culture is characterized by extended family life, homogamy in the creation of families, and the preeminence of parents in the creation of new families. By and large, the community values monogamous families and gender segregation in education. Existing studies have confirmed that Muslim Meskhetians have not assimilated for years in their host countries, including Georgia, where they have lived since the 1970s (Sumbadze, 2007). Due to the compact settlement of Muslim Meskhetians, the process of integration with the local population proved difficult in Georgia and depended largely on the perceptions and attitudes of all members of the community, new arrivals as well as local Georgians (Sumbadze, 2007).

General data of Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia

The process of locating data about Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia is challenging. For example, the National Statistics Office of Georgia does not have official data on the number of Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia. Researchers were able to locate data from "Tolerant,"⁴ a non-governmental organization lo-

cated in Akhaltsikhe. As described in *Tab. N1*, data collected and published by Tolerant in 2012 verifies the number of Muslim Meskhetian families in the Georgian territory.

The 2017 data in *Tab. N1* was compiled with data supplied by Mr. Irakli Kokaia,⁵ Head of the Refugee and Repatriation Division of the Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Accommodation and Refugees of Georgia.

Tab.N1.

Accommodation of Muslim Meskhetians 2012-2017

Municipality	Family	Total	Man	Women		Family	Total	Man	Women
	2012					2017			
Ianeti, Samtredia	30	163	91	72		36	175	83	92
Nasakirali, Ozurgeti	32	151	76	75		24	117	62	55
Akhaltzikhe	26	123	84	57		60	260	124	136
Cori	12	49	25	24		4	18	8	10
Tbilisi	15	57	35	28		10	40	18	22
Total	115	543	263	282		134	610	295	315

Since 2012 and at the time of this study, 16 families and 56 individuals have arrived in Georgia. According to collected data on the total number of Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia, 40% of the total population participated in this research study.

General Findings of Qualitative and Quantitative study

The number of quantitative study participants totaled 250 Muslim Meskhetians, 57.4% of whom are female and 42.6% male.

Georgia's Repatriation Law (known as the *Law on the Repatriation of Persons Involuntarily Displaced by the Former USSR from the Georgian USSR in the 1940's*) began its implementation process in 2012. Through the process, the Georgian government facilitated Muslim Meskhetian resettlement.

The country has adjusted the legal framework, as far as the practice is concerned, about 5,000 applicants have applied, more precisely 4,844 adults. Their number with the nation of children was somewhere around 9,000, and in fact from every country where they live, except the United States of America.

Muslim Meskhetians who arrived after implementation of the 2012 Repatriation Law, received Georgian citizenship. Some Muslim Meskhetian families decided to return by themselves prior to the law's implementation and preferred living in southwest Georgia, their ancestral homeland. They bought private houses and land and still reside in those areas today. In contrast, some of Muslim Meskhetians who came by themselves between 2000-2012 have experienced difficulty in obtaining citizenship. The difficulties are related to dual citizenship, some countries of residence of Muslim Meskhetian do not allow dual citizenship with Georgia.

General Findings and Discussion

Muslim Meskhetian ethnic identity have different opinions about its manifestation according to the scholars (Trier, at all 2007) during the decades.

Over the years Muslim Meskhetians have been referred to in scientific sources as "Meskhetian Turks."

In Georgian historical sources, they are called "Muslim Georgians," or "ethnic Georgians" who lived in Samtskhe-Javakheti, and who experienced occupation by the Ottoman Empire for nearly three centuries (VI-VIII). According to Georgian historical sources, living under occupation influenced their lives, faith, and language (Sumbadze, 2007; Maglakelidze, 1994; Nozadze, 1989).

What is the definition of Georgian identity? Who is a Georgian? For Georgians, religion and language are integral parts of a Georgian identity, and equally important as homeland. According to the common opinion in Georgia, this is a person who speaks Georgian and is an Orthodox Christian. (Chxartishvili, 2008. pp.224 - 225; BogiSvil., at all 2016. pp.70-75) According to identity scholars, „ statement about the foundational elements of nationhood: "land, language and religion/beliefs", is often referred to as the motto of "Georgianness" (Gamsakhurdia., 2020).

Now, Muslim Meskhetians largely consider themselves belonging one of two delineations of ethnic identity: ascribing either Georgian "orientation," and historically recognizing their Georgian origin, or identifying as Turks from Akhaltsikhe „Ahiska Turks “. It should be noted that Akhaltsikhe is the toponymic name of the district in south west of Georgia, which in Georgian is called Akhaltsikhe which is translated as „ New Castle. “

After multiple turmoil of this society in different time during the centuries, the part of this society moved finally to Georgia and are continuing life there. The present research try study Muslim meskhetian identity in their homeland – in Georgia. How they are integrating now in Georgia, How they are filing about their identity and how they are manifesting verbally about identity now in Georgia.

⁴ "Tolenarti" Association of Samtskhe -Javakheti <http://asociacia-toleranti.blogspot.com/>

⁵ Irakli kokaia. Head of the Refugee and Repatriation division, Ministry of Internally Displaced Persons from the Occupied Territories, Accommodation and Refugees of Georgia; <http://mra.gov.ge/eng/static/661>

For Muslim Mekhsetians living in Georgia means integrate in this social environment. How we will call this process - integration or re-integration depends on how they try to establish themselves and realize their identity in the environment.

According to MC. La Barbera (ed. (2015) "Identity encompasses the multiple roles endorsed by individuals in social life that are externalized through the use of markers, such as language, dress, and occupation of space. Drawing on social psychology, sociology, anthropology, political sciences, and feminist studies, the concept of identity that grounds this volume is a complex social phenomenon resulting from constant negotiations among personal conditions, social relationships, and institutional frameworks."

The process of integration depends on the language competence of individuals in the national language of the country in which a person lives. This language competence depends not only on secondary education in that language, but also on the language people use to communicate with at home. In case of Muslim Meskhetians, National language competence continues to be a challenge for Muslim Meskhetians in Georgia. When asked which language they use at home, the majority of participants indicated that they speak Turkish Anatolian Dialect at home. Only a few families speak in Georgian with their family members. In summary, 89% of participants use the Anatolian dialect of the Turkish language at home. Fewer than 9% say that they speak Georgian at home. Even fewer use Russian as a colloquial language.

The colloquial language spoken at home is an indicator of ethnic identity for many cultures. For the majority of Muslim Meskhetians research participants, answering questions about both identity and language was met with some discomfort. Formerly, the only segment of the population who could speak in Georgian were young schoolchildren (Sumbadze 2007; pp214), but today many more people, including elders, speak Georgian.

"Now more of our people are speaking the Georgian language. We studied Georgian language in high school. Our children begin speaking the language in kindergarten and use it every day throughout school. Our parents now speak Georgian instead of Russian. When they arrived, they did not speak the language, but today it is different." (37-year-old male in Georgia)

As Sumbadze (2007) argues, the ethnic identity of Muslim Meskhetians is different and has changed over time. Those residing in Georgia most commonly claim their ancestors as Georgian, while others identify with other ethnic groups (pp. 227-228).

Muslim Meskhetian ethnic identity is heavily influenced by displacement itself:

"Some of them call us Tatars, some of them call us Turks. Sometimes we are identified by place of residence--Azerbaijan Turks, Uzbekistan Turks, Turkmenistan Turks--because of language." (68-year-old female in Georgia via Sumbadze 2007 pp.228)

"I am a Turk. I was born in Uzbekistan, live in Krasnodar, and my homeland is Georgia. But I am a US citizen. I do not have a homeland in my view. Can

you tell me where my homeland is? I can't." (39 - year-old male in the United States (Pirtskhalava 2018. pp.8)

Sometimes identity is ascribed strategically as a method of accessing resources (Sumbadze 2007 pp. 228). With such disputes over identity itself, Muslim Meskhetians may identify as Georgian when accessing Georgian resources or community and Turkish when accessing Turkish resources or community as a means of gaining support, connection, or legibility.

To determine ethnic identity, participants were asked questions about how they identify themselves. The possible descriptions included "Ahiska Turk" (Turk from Akhaltsikhe), "Georgian," or "Turk." More than half of the participants identified themselves as Ahiska Turks (57.9%). This ethnic group dislikes being referred to as Meskhetian Turks and some of them (mostly those living in other countries) consider being referred to as Georgian incorrect.

"We are Turks but not from Turkey, we are from Ahiska, and we are "Ahiska Turk"- (50 years old-Male)

According to my previous study in the USA (Pirtskhalava2018) 62-years - old - Muslim Meskhetian woman who is living in Pennsylvania state US, did not know what is the meaning of "Ahiska" but she defines themselves identity like this. Muslim Meskhetians who are living in Georgia, have been in Akhaltsikhe and in the villages around of this at least once. They were living in different villages in Akhaltsikhe district, but they are putting in the label of identity (place) main town of those district.

What is the marker being of "Ahiska Turk" for Muslim Meskhetians?

Discussing about of this marker of identity for the deported people as a community, have a history of Muslimization in the 16-17th century, during Ottoman occupation, of multiple forced migration and displacement experiences, analyzing the difficulty of combining different understanding nationality and identity. In on the one hand, being a Georgian and on the other hand, being Turkish.

According to Gregory Goalwin (2018) "For residents of the former Ottoman Empire, religion became synonymous with national identity, and all those who fell outside the boundaries of the religious ingroup simultaneously faced exclusion from the national community". For Yusuf Akçura the relationship between religion and nationalism in the Muslim world is "One of the fundamental tenets of Islam is expressed in the saying 'religion and nation are one'" (1981). Taking these considerations into account, living under Ottoman occupation during 2 century's (1578 – 1878) had influence of identity perception.

The conceptualization of the Georgian nation with the reinterpretation of the main ethnic markers Georgian is a person who was born in Georgia, speaks in Georgian language and is an Orthodox Christian. "Ilia Chavchavadze's statement about the foundational elements of nationhood: "Land, Language and Religion/beliefs", is often referred to as the motto of "Georgianness" argues Gamsakhurdia (2020). Nowadays among the Muslim Meskhetians only small group

speaks in Georgian (according most of respondents narratives their grandparents spoke fluently), all of them are Muslims and this is how they differ from the majority of Georgians in Georgia, but It should be noted that, the Muslim Georgians are living in Georgia, in Achara district - in the neighboring area of Meskhet- Javakheti, from where are Muslim Meskhetians, and this part of Georgia was under Ottoman occupation, but during 1614- 1878 They lost their Christianity but kept Georgian language. Muslim Meskhetians lost both of them, and finally by decision Soviet government lost land (deported from the homeland).

It can be assumed that one of the reasons for Muslim Meskhetian being the "Ahiska Turk" and not a Georgian or a Turk from Turkey is different meaning of ethnicity or nationality from point of view of Turks and of Georgians.

In the other hands from my point of view the "Ahiska Turks" identity is fraught with the psychological trauma of multiple displacement accompanied difficult conditions.

The deportation of Muslim Meskhetians from Georgia came with little explanation and the community is still grappling with the emotional scars of deportation and the historical legacies of forced displacement and subsequent trauma.

As Aydin (2017) describes, "psychological trauma is a type of damage that violates the familiar ideas and expectations about the world of an individual or society, plunging them into a state of extreme confusion and uncertainty. War or other types of mass violence (genocide, deportation) often cause trauma that, besides individuals, involves a society or a culture" (Bessel & Van Der Kolk, 1987, pp. 1–30).

The traumatic event, as deportation, which is shared by a group of people scholars refer with few existing concepts of "collective trauma" (Hirschberger 2018) "chosen trauma" (Volkan 2001) "cultural trauma" (Alexander 2004) "Psychological trauma and cultural trauma" (Smelser 2004) or "societal/social trauma" (Suedfel 1997).

According to scholars (Muldoon at all (2009,2013.,2019)work the political situation has a numbing effect on the identity, the trauma which is the result of the life experience, has an impact on the identity, and according to it can be explained that the new group created by the internal homogeneity of the group - Ahikha Turks, for the part of which lives in Georgia, Georgianness is more a social identity, than an ethnic one.

The obtained results of this research are an indicator of this.

Because of unity with that group is represented in this way, even though the Muslim Meskhetians who are of the "Georgian orientation" put Georgianness first, still Turkishness is an important aspect of their unity with a homogeneous group, which not only unites the

residents of Georgia but everyone who was deported from Georgia as a result of political persecution.

The history of displacement this population gives reason to think about traumatization. The deportation from homeland (1944) as "undesirable peoples", was deported from the Caucasus to the Central Asia (Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan), the other displacement because of conflict with indigenous group (local Central Asian population) (1989) after relocation one part of population moved to Azerbaijan, the other part to Krasnodarsky district of Russia, the later repatriation to homeland but not to the place of origin.

Many still ask "what have we done/we done to deserve this?"

It can be argued that identifying themselves as Ahikha Turks could be both a psychological defense mechanism in response to trauma and directly linked to the phenomenon of "place identity" (Cuba and Hummon 1993a, 1993b). It should be noted that the participants of the qualitative research (who were the same participants involved in the quantitative research) mostly referred to themselves in qualitative interviews as Georgian.

"Why do you always ask this? We are Georgians and we returned to Georgia and have lived in Georgia. For so many years, we were living in a different place. We speak Russian very well and our "Meskhetians".⁶ After returning to our homeland, we've been learning Georgian and our children and grandchildren speak the language very well." (67-year-old male in Georgia)

"Why do all the researchers who study us after coming back to Georgia ask the same question, 'how do we identify ourselves?' I say to them and you, again and again, we are Georgians, Meskhs, but we speak Turkish. We call it Meskhetian's language."⁷ (60-year-old male in Georgia)

"Some of our people don't know our history very well, because they have made mistakes. We know better, our grandparents tell us about our origin and history. The Soviet government had an impact on our people's minds, but we know exactly who we are." (29-year-old male)

Muslim Meskhetians in Akhaltsikhe repatriated earlier than those living in the western part of Georgia, and their adaptation process is currently underway. Most Muslim Meskhetians arrived after 2008 and 2012, but some have been living in Georgia since 1980. Data analysis suggests that religious identity saliency for newcomers is underscored by living in a new social environment where the majority are Orthodox Christians. Yet, for residents who are more adapted and integrated, civic identity is more salient.

"Twenty Statements" Test is used to investigate self-identities, as well as roles and role priorities. The participants answer up to twenty responses to the prompts, "Who am I?" or "I am..." According to authors Kuhn (1960), the twenty statements test should be

⁶ The participant is referring to Anatolian dialects of Turkish.

⁷ According to Muslim Meskhetians "Meskhetian language" here refers to Kartvelian languages. In the Republic of Georgia Georgian language is State Language but there are two another Kartvelian languages which don't have script: Megre-

lian (spoken by Georgian population living in Samegrelo-region of Georgia) and Svan (spoken by Georgian population living in Svaneti -Region of Georgia) which comes from the names of the regions where this region is located, Samegrelo and Svaneti).

grouped into five categories: Social groups and classifications; Ideological beliefs; Interests; Ambition; and Self-evaluations. This research study employs the “Twenty Statements” Test as a methodology to unearth how research subjects formulate their identities.

The Social identity complexity theory underlines the ways in which the various group identities interact, seeking to understand how individuals construct social identities in relation to multiple nonconvergent ingroup memberships (Roccas and Brewer 2002).

According to the Twenty statement test, most of the Muslim Meskhetians primarily identify themselves with the social roles they have. In second place is identifying oneself with the Muslim religion, meaning that religious belief is one of the main components of the identity, for 18,6% is important in their identity Meskhetians as group identity, only 9.3 % of participants say that they are Georgians, 5.5 % Georgian citizens, and only 1.1% say that they are Georgian Meskhetians. Only one of the participants in the survey claimed Meskhetian Turk identity.

The data generated from the “Twenty Statements” Test forms an order based on designated importance. As the test adaptation in Georgia has shown, people often name the following categories: *professional identity, family role, status, gender, and age*. Among the identities named by Muslim Meskhetian participants, the family role holds an important position. Religion is also highlighted, which takes second place in most cases and is given greater significance than ethnic or civic identity.

Through analyzing data gathered from the Bogardus Social Distance Scale and qualitative interviews, it can be said that the most salient identity (Encyclopedia of Identity 2010) for Muslim Meskhetians is their religious identity. **Social distance** is an important measure to find out how open people are to becoming close to people who are ethnically or socially different from themselves. The Bogardus Social Distance Scale (1924) is used as a scale that measures varying degrees of closeness in people towards other members of diverse social, ethnic and racial groups. Measuring social distance can show how people are integrated into the social environment.

According to the data, the majority of relationships and contact are with those who share their religious identity. In this way, marriages and starting families is most approved of by family members if marriage partners are both Muslim Meskhetians. If not Muslim Meskhetian, approval is secondarily given to marriage arrangements between a Muslim Meskhetian and an Orthodox Christian Georgian, followed by marriage to someone who is Azerbaijani, Turk, or Adjarian (Muslim Georgian). The positioning of marriage to Orthodox Christian Georgians as secondary to Muslim Meskhetian marriages contradicts researchers’ observations that there are few, if any, marriages with non-Muslim Meskhetians, and in the handful of instances, more inter-ethnic Muslim Meskhetian marriages with other Muslims than inter-ethnic marriages with Orthodox Christian Georgians.

On this scale we put a diversity of ethnic identities of those who live in Georgia, including Adjarians (eco migrants from Adjara⁸ living in Guria), who are ethnically Georgian and religiously Sunni Muslims. Some Adjarians reside alongside Muslim Meskhetians in the Ozurgeti districts (specifically Guria) where repatriated Muslim Meskhetians had taken up residence in the 1980s. In recognition of the importance of Muslim Meskhetian religious identity, we divided Georgians according to religion to encourage a deeper understanding of social distance.

On the Bogardus Social Distance Scale, the participants’ desire to have close contact with representatives of the same group (other Muslim Meskhetians) is highest. Relationships with Orthodox Christian Georgians take second place for them, followed by those with Azerbaijani, Turk, and Muslim Adjarian populations. The participants showed the least interest in having close contact with the Kurdish and Roma people ethnic groups (both national minorities who live in Georgia). Based on these results, we can say *that ethnic identity determines their contact proximity more than their religious identity*.

According to the data of the Bogardus Social Distance Scale, Muslim Meskhetians would most readily consent to establish a family or would approve of the marriage of a family member if the partner were Muslim Meskhetian; followed by Orthodox Christian Georgian. Yet, participant observation does not reflect this claim, as there is only a small percentage of marriages and families made with Orthodox Georgians, while in contrast, Adjarians, who are Muslim Georgians and share the Sunni Muslim religion with Muslim Meskhetians, are marrying at higher rates than inter-ethnic Orthodox Georgians when residing in the same villages. In other words, marrying within the religion seems preferable.

When it comes to friendship, the data shows that younger generations have more Georgian friends than older generations. Evidence suggests that attitudes depend heavily on exposure and access to relationships with people of different ethnic groups. The younger generation of Muslim Meskhetians born in Georgia have more openness and are likely to have Georgian friends in high school, Georgian neighbors, and daily interactions that give way to regular communication and access to relationship-building. Muslim Meskhetians have relatives in Azerbaijan and visit to attend a wedding or funeral. Other Muslim Meskhetians visit Turkey as seasonal migrant laborers. One can anticipate that the low rates of willingness to have contact with Roma people may be simply because the majority of Muslim Meskhetians never have interacted with the Roma people population.

Notably, participants emphasize the impact that the return to Georgia has had on their lives:

“I am very happy my parents decided to live in Georgia. When I visit relatives in Azerbaijan and come back home, I always say thank you to my grandfather and my parents because women live so much freer here, compared to where my relatives live abroad. There is a

⁸ AdJara, Guria, Samegrelo, Svaneti, Mekheti are regions of Georgia

normal life here and good people. I can be educated. I can dress however I want. I still get my parent's permission, but I can go where I want to go." (17-year-old female in Georgia)

The tradition of establishing a Muslim Meskhetian family is largely uninfluenced by integration. By and large, it is still the case that Muslim Meskhetians create families only with other Muslim Meskhetians. It is a rarity to see Muslim Meskhetians marrying "non-Meskhetians." According to the data, religion plays a leading role in such cases. In Samtredia and Osurgeti there are small cases where families have Adjarian daughters-in-law. The tradition of marrying Meskhetians with Meskhetians was also maintained during displacement (Sumbadze 2007).

Concerning differences between the gender of participants, this data shows that females consider marriage with an Orthodox Christian Georgian more acceptable than males. The difference between the genders on the acceptability of marriage between a relative with an Azerbaijani is even higher, with more females approving of this marriage arrangement than males. Meanwhile, a relative getting married to an Adjarian is more acceptable for males than females. The answer of the question *I would give consent if my relative got married with* – 98.7% of female and 98.1 Male respondents first answer was Meskhetians, the second Georgian (43.4 and 39), Than Aseri (42.1; 32.7) and Turks (32.9 32.4)

Summary

Muslim Meskhetians living in Georgia have largely preserved the cultural and social practices that had been important to them before, during, and after deportation. When it comes to the question of what has changed for Muslim Meskhetians as a result of integration and adaptation, the answer is both a detailing of what is transforming and what endures. While Muslim Meskhetians continue to preserve and prioritize intra-group relationships and religious community ties, the community is also increasingly speaking in the state language (Georgian), forming community with the broader Georgian population, and claiming Georgian citizenship and a sense of belonging and integration in Georgian society.

While the results of the research show, that for the majority of Muslim Meskhetians, religious identity continues to be more salient than civic identity. When it comes to relationships, this study has shown, that while Muslim Meskhetians still largely marry within their community, they are slowly becoming more integrated with the rest of Georgian society. They are forming friendships with people from other ethnic groups, and the younger generation is growing up with significant language acquisition and cultural influence from the broader Georgian population. As the younger generation continues to age, one can anticipate greater integration into Georgian society through shared language, community, and participation.

Identifying as Ahiska Turks for Muslim Meskhetians can be viewed as a direct response to the psychological trauma of decades marked by forced removal, displacement, and the long repatriation process. That is,

place – in this case, Ahitska (Akhhaltsikhe) – became positioned at the core of emotional attachment for Muslim Meskhetians (Cuba and Hummon 1993a, 1993b; Giuliani 2003; Hernández et al. 2007). Therefore, reclaiming Akhhaltsikhe can be viewed as both a trauma response (Aydin 2017) and defense mechanism in addition to providing a pathway of return for the displaced. Muslim Meskhetians are engaged in the construction of what is referred to as "imagined community" (Anderson 1991) by collectively imagining an Ahiska Turk identity, an identity that allows them to re-envision their religion as historically Muslim (Pirtskhgalava 2018) and deeply connected to home.

This can be seen in the framework of two theories, the common ingroup identity (CIIM; Gaertner and Dovidio's (2000) and the ingroup projection (IPM; Mummendey & Wenzel, 1999) model. The collective trauma caused by the political situation, the cause of which has not been explained to them, led to ethnic separation from the main group and identification with another larger group based on religious indicators.

The identification with the common group "Ahitska Turks", in which all deportee's population from Meskhetia are united, which is tied to the place and forms the identity of the place (mein town of Meskhetia - Akhhaltsikhe) instead of the national identity, the non-acceptance of Georgianness (be Georgian) may be due to group attitudes. In the variant of intra-group presentation, „Turkishness“ - (be Turks), as well as membership of a social group, is presented as part of a large powerful group, but again not in ethnicity.

In my opinion, the place identity is the solution to overcome this ambivalence for Muslim Meskhetian.

The integration (Berry 1997) process for Muslim Meskhetians is marked by both the maintenance of original culture and the adoption of key aspects of the communities. Integration is both an ongoing process and a reciprocal process, in which receiving societies adapt to new immigrant populations, and knowing the language, participating in education and communication with local inhabitants play important roles in integrating communities (Gordon, M.1964; Berry, J.1997; Augoustinos & Innes, 1990; Moscovici, 1981; Hooward, 2000). The integration process is not facilitated by simply living in the territory. As research shows, language acquisition plays a major role in the process. In this case, Georgian language acquisition is an essential catalyst for communication and access to education, another critical part of integration. As education gives way to deeper civic identity formation, more robust connections with the local community, and increased access to resources, more integration follows.

In summary, the story of Muslim Meskhetians reflects both significant cultural preservation and the slow impact of integration and cultural adaptation. As time goes on, the data indicates increased integration is on the horizon.

Future Directions for Research

Future research in the form of longitudinal studies can work to trace these changes over time, including the distinct ways in which preservation and integration may influence one another. Moreover, future directions for research can include a deeper exploration of

whether and how rescripting displaced identity via the “place identity” (in this case the Ahiska Turk identity) may function to redress trauma and reclaim territory and religious identity. Moreover, longitudinal studies exploring how younger Muslim Meskhetians navigate both their history and future will lay the groundwork for understanding how this population grapples with reclaiming place and belonging in the aftermath of displacement.

Limitation of Research

One primary research limitation of this study is that the researchers were non-Muslim Georgians and therefore occupy a different positionality in relation to integration itself. Despite that fieldwork was conducted with the help of an interpreter, researchers also believe that not being able to communicate in Turkish languages impacted qualitative interviewing with Muslim Meskhetians who arrived after 2012 and are less likely to speak Georgian.

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